

Insect Juvenile Hormone Analogues. Part-XXII. Syntheses of Some Long Chain *N*-Alkylated Succinimides and Their Derivatives

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Syntheses of some long chain *N*-alkylated succinimides from geraniol, 4,8-dimethyl-3(*E*), 7-nonadien-1-ol, 5,9-dimethyl 4(*E*), 8-decadien-1-ol and 2-geranylthioethan-1-ol and their various derivatives are reported.

In recent years¹⁻³, much attention has been given to the synthesis and screening of juvenile hormone mimics. In order to study the influence of structural modifications on juvenile hormone mimics and their activities, we wish to report the preparations and JH activity of different *N*-alkylated succinimides and their derivatives.

Succinamide was alkylated⁴ with geraniol (1) in the presence of triphenylphosphine in anhydrous THF containing diethylazodicarboxylate to furnish *N*-(3,7-dimethyl-2(*E*), 6-octadienyl)succinimide (5) which on treatment with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid⁵ in equimolar amounts in anhydrous methylene chloride yielded the monoepoxy derivative (9) after column chromatography over florisil

Compound 5 on reaction with ethyl diazoacetate⁶ in the presence of anhydrous CuSO₄ gave *N*-(3,7-dimethyl-6,7-carbomethoxymethylene-2(*E*)-octenyl)succinimide (13). Similarly, 4,8-dimethyl-3(*E*), 7-nonadien-1-ol (2) (prepared by the reduction of homogeryl ester with LAH in ether suspension), 5,9-dimethyl-4(*E*), 8-decadien-1-ol (3) and 2-geranylthioethan-1-ol (5) (prepared by the LAH reduction of ethyl-2-geranyl acetate in ether) were coupled with succinamide to give their respective imides (6-8). The imides (6-8) were transformed into their monoepoxy derivatives (10, 11). In case of imide (8) having sulphur atom in the chain, sulphoxide (12) was formed instead of epoxide with one equivalent of *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid. Terminal double bond in 6-8 were modified into carbomethoxymethylene moiety thus furnishing derivatives 14-16.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	Eluent pet. ether: ether 60-80°	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
				C	H
5					
6	9 : 1	48	C ₁₇ H ₂₈ NO ₂	70.20 (72.25)	9.35 (9.80)
7	17 : 3	50	C ₁₈ H ₃₀ NO ₂	72.90 (72.96)	9.50 (9.57)
8	4 : 1	52	C ₁₉ H ₃₂ NO ₂ S	65.15 (65.06)	8.45 (8.58)
10	17 : 3	70	C ₁₇ H ₂₈ NO ₂	67.80 (67.89)	8.60 (8.74)
11	4 : 1	68	C ₁₈ H ₃₀ NO ₂	68.80 (68.78)	9.10 (9.02)
12	3 : 1	65	C ₁₈ H ₃₀ NO ₂ S	61.65 (61.71)	8.00 (8.09)
14	4 : 1	50	C ₁₈ H ₃₀ NO ₂	68.00 (68.02)	8.65 (8.71)
15	7 : 3	48	C ₂₀ H ₃₄ NO ₂	68.80 (68.74)	8.80 (8.94)
16	3 : 2	52	C ₂₀ H ₃₄ NO ₂ S	62.79 (62.97)	8.21 (8.19)

All the compounds (tlc pure) were tested for their JH activity against *Dysdercus koenigii fabricus* according to the procedure reported in the literature^{8,9}. Farnesyl methyl ether was used as

standard (JH score = 4.00)¹⁰. The screening results are given in Table 2. Activity indices value show

TABLE 2—JH ACTIVITY OF VARIOUS COMPOUNDS

No. of insects used = 10, dose = 1% in acetone (6 μ l)

Compd. no.	Dead	Activity response				Activity index	
		0	1	2	3		
5	0	7	0	1	2	0	0.80
9	0	6	0	0	4	0	1.20
13	0	0	0	0	4	6	3.60
6	1	5	0	1	3	0	1.22
10	1	4	1	1	2	1	1.44
14	0	6	1	1	2	0	0.90
7	0	7	1	1	1	0	0.60
11	0	5	1	1	2	0	0.90
15	0	8	0	1	1	0	0.50
8	1	6	1	0	2	0	0.77
12	1	5	1	1	2	0	1.00
16	1	6	0	0	3	0	1.00

that epoxy and carbethoxymethylene derivatives are more active than their parent compounds.

The spectral data of the imides and their derivatives were consistent with their structures. Spectral data in a few representative have been given.

4,8-Dimethyl-3(E),7-nonadien-1-ol (2): 4,8-Dimethyl-3(E),7-nonadienoic acid¹¹ (homogeranic acid) was converted to its ethyl ester by the usual procedure, (80%), b.p. 72-72°/5-7 mm.

To a well stirred suspension of LAH (2.26 g) in anhyd. ether (250 ml) was added the ester (13.75 g) in anhyd. ether (30 ml) slowly. The mixture was stirred for 2 h and left overnight. Thereafter, it was refluxed for 3 h, cooled and decomposed with saturated aqueous sodium potassium tartarate solution. The organic layer was separated and dried. The solvent was evaporated and the residue was distilled under reduced pressure to give the alcohol (2) as a colourless viscous liquid (70%, 7.54 g), b.p. 95-97°/5-7 mm (Found: C, 78.40; H, 11.88. $C_{11}H_{20}O$ requires C, 78.51; H, 11.98%). ν_{max} 3600, 3450, 2970, 2850, 1440, 1360, 1170, 1120, 1050 and 980 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 1.67 (9H, allylic methyls), 2.1-2.3 (6H, allylic methylenes) and 3.0-3.35 (3H, $-CH_2-OH$).

2-Geranyl-thioethan-1-ol (4): Geranyl thioacetic acid¹² was first converted into its ethyl ester and hence, reduced to its corresponding alcohol according to the usual procedure given above, (74%), (Found: C, 67.15; H, 10.16. $C_{12}H_{22}SO$ requires C, 67.29; H, 10.28%). ν_{max} 3350, 2850, 1595, 1495, 1430, 1390, 1308, 1295, 1100, 1040 and 810 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 1.63 (9H, allylic methyls), 2.05 (4H, allylic methylenes), 3.1-3.9 (7H, $-CH_2-S-CH_2-OH$) and 5.2-5.35 (2H, olefinic protons).

N-(3,7-Dimethyl-2(E),6-octadienyl-succinimide (5): To a stirred mixture of succinamide (6.0 g), triphenylphosphine (12.0 g) and geraniol (7.2 g) in anhyd. THF (90 ml) was added dropwise a solution of diethylazodicarboxylate (8.4 g) in anhyd. THF (10 ml) at 0°. The reaction mixture was stirred for

18 h at room temperature. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure to afford a semisolid mass, which was diluted with chloroform, washed successively with aqueous NaOH solution (1 N), brine, saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and dried. After the removal of the solvent followed by column chromatography of the residue over silica gel using petroleum ether-ether (19:1) as the eluent, furnished compound (5) (50%, 4.57 g) (Found: C, 71.40; H, 9.10. $C_{14}H_{21}NO_2$ requires C, 71.45; H, 9.00%). ν_{max} 3010, 2975, 2945, 2860, 1760, 1710, 1450, 1400, 1340, 1250, 1166, 1058, 1000, 880, 820 and 663 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 1.50 (6H, s, terminal methyls), 1.75 (3H, s, olefinic methyl), 1.95-2.20 (4H, allylic methylenes), 2.70 (4H, s, succinimide methylene protons), 4.20 (2H, d, J 7.5 Hz, CH_2-N) and 4.9-5.4 (2H, olefinic protons). Similarly, alcohols 2-4 were condensed with succinamide under the same reaction conditions as used for the preparation of 5, to yield the compounds 6-8, respectively.

N-(3,7-Dimethyl-6,7-epoxy-2(E)-octenyl)-succinimide (9): *m*-Chloroperbenzoic acid (1.10 g) in methylene chloride (20 ml) was added dropwise to a well stirred mixture of 5 (2.0 g) at 0° and the stirring was continued for 30 min more. The reaction mixture was then successively washed with saturated solution of $NaHCO_3$, water and brine. The organic layer was dried over anhyd. $CaCl_2$ and the solvent evaporated. Chromatography of the residue over florisil and elution with petroleum ether-ether (4:1) yielded 9 (70%, 1.5 g) (Found: C, 66.88; H, 8.40. $C_{14}H_{21}NO_2$ requires C, 66.90; H, 8.42%). ν_{max} 3010, 2975, 2945, 2855, 1760, 1710, 1450, 1400, 1340, 1250, 1160, 1050, 1000, 980 and 800 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 1.35 (6H, s, terminal methyls), 1.5-2.30 (7H, olefinic methyl and methylene protons), 2.65-2.75 (5H, 1H, epoxy methine and 4H, succinimide methylene protons), 4.28 (2H, d, J 8 Hz, CH_2-N), 5.35 (1H, t like, olefinic proton).

Compounds 6-8 were subjected to epoxidation under similar conditions as reported for the compound 5 to yield mono-epoxy compounds (10, 11). However, the compound 8 gave sulphoxide (12), on epoxidation with one equivalent of *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid.

N-(3,7-Dimethyl-6,7-carbethoxymethylene-2(E)-octenyl)succinimide (13): To a well stirred mixture of the compound 5 (1.0 g), and freshly prepared anhyd. $CuSO_4$ (1.36 g) was added dropwise a mixture of imide (5; 1.0 g) and ethyldiazoacetate (0.49 g) at 90°. The stirring was continued at that temperature for 2 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and diluted with ether, filtered and the organic layer was dried. Removal of the solvent followed by chromatography over silica gel using petroleum ether-ether (7:3) as eluent furnished the product 13, (50%, 1.35 g) (Found: C, 67.20; H, 8.44. $C_{14}H_{21}NO_4$ requires C, 67.26; H, 8.47%). ν_{max} 3010, 2970, 2850, 1760, 1735, 1710, 1450, 1400, 1340, 1250, 1160, 1050, 1030 and 830 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 1.25 (3H, t, $-CHCOOCH_2CH_3$), 1.35 (6H, s, terminal methyls), 1.5-2.30 (7H, olefinic methyl and

methylene protons), 2.70 (4H, s, succinimide methylene protons), 4.28 (2H, d, J 7.5 Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{-N}$), 4.4 (2H, q, $\text{HCCOOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$) and 6.00 (1H, $\text{CHCOOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$).

Similarly, compounds 6-8, on treatment with ethyldiazoacetate in the presence of freshly prepared anhyd. CuSO_4 afforded 14-16 under similar reaction conditions, respectively.

Analytical data of all the compounds is given in Table 1.

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